

**PURPOSE, OBJECTIVES, RELATION WITH OTHER
SUBJECTS OF THE METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING THE
UZBEK LANGUAGE**

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada til imkoniyatlari, ijodiy tafakkur sohibi, kommunikativ savodxonlik, pedagogik texnologiya, ongli verbal kognitiv ta'lim to'g'risida yoritib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Til imkoniyatlari, ijodiy tafakkur sohibi, kommunikativ savodxonlik, pedagogik texnologiya, ongli verbal kognitiv ta'lim, amaliy maqsad, ta'limiy maqsad, rivojlantiruvchi maqsad.

Аннотация: В данной статье описаны языковые возможности, творческое мышление, коммуникативная грамотность, педагогические технологии, сознательное словесно-познавательное образование.

Ключевые слова: Речевые возможности, творческое мышление, коммуникативная грамотность, педагогическая технология, сознательное словесно-познавательное образование, практическая цель, воспитательная цель, развивающая цель.

Annotation: This article describes language capabilities, creative thinking, communicative literacy, pedagogical technology, and conscious verbal cognitive education.

Key words: Language capabilities, creative thinking, communicative literacy, pedagogical technology, conscious verbal cognitive education, practical purpose, educational purpose, developmental purpose.

In honor of independence, major reforms are being carried out in the field of

education. Since the first days of independence, serious attention has been paid to the upbringing of the younger generation. The enactment of the Law "On Education", "National Training Program", "State Educational Standards" is characterized as the most important stage in these processes. These documents also establish a number of requirements for teaching in the mother tongue. On this basis, programs and textbooks in the native language were also updated. Two generations of updated native language textbooks have been published and introduced into teaching. The views and requirements for teaching the mother tongue have changed. Textbooks were created based on these requirements.

Although the methodology of teaching the native language as a pedagogical subject has accumulated a wealth of experience, a number of problems have arisen in connection with the teaching of this subject. The reason for this is that a number of modern technologies have entered and are included in the educational process, textbooks of the native language of general education schools have been updated, textbooks have been created for academic lyceums and professional colleges. Views and analyzes related to this, guidelines should be the subject of study of the methods of teaching the Uzbek language.

In this sense, the content of this subject can be defined as follows: the development of a consistent system of teaching the native language, the selection and implementation of methodological recommendations for organizing classes in the native language, as well as modern pedagogical technologies in the field of methodology. , interactive methods of teaching a language is to develop the scientific foundations reflected in it. This subject is aimed at introducing the acquired knowledge into pedagogical practice, effective use of advanced pedagogical technologies. The methodology of teaching the Uzbek language studies the didactic foundations of the formation of creative thinking. Scientific method of teaching the native language to the younger generation: what?, how

much?, how? answers questions that need to be taught. Learning how to teach a language means finding, choosing and putting into practice the appropriate methods for different stages of learning.

The main goal of the methodology for teaching the Uzbek language is to develop students' skills and abilities for the correct, accurate, appropriate and effective use of language capabilities, the development of logical and creative thinking, increasing communicative literacy, and the formation of national independence among students. in the formation of ideas and spiritual enrichment of the student's personality.

The main objective of the language teaching methodology is to educate students who are able to freely, creatively and independently express their thoughts orally and in writing, based on the norms of the literary language, and who have the ability to convey the same meaning in different situations.

The science of the methodology of teaching the Uzbek language has its own theoretical foundations and scientific research methods. These are: 1. Observation. Linguists and methodologists read, listen to and follow methodical articles and lectures given at scientific conferences, periodicals and pedagogical research, observe modern models of lessons and draw appropriate conclusions from them. With the help of this method, the problems associated with teaching the native language are taught, new views and methods are determined.

2. Experiment. Methodist scientists share the results of their scientific research at scientific conferences and test the methods that they propose and want to use in certain schools or academic lyceums, based on reasonable and reliable criteria. They analyze the results. This method creates the basis for proving the reliability and validity of the recommended scientific and methodological hypotheses.

3. Testing. With the help of this method, theoretical knowledge, skills and

abilities of students are studied. Conducting control questions allows you to make generalized conclusions about the knowledge and acquired practical skills of students.

4. Distribution of questionnaires and questionnaires. With the help of this method, the attitude, interests and desires of teachers and students towards science are studied.

5. Educational and methodological heritage. Although the history of teaching the native language dates back to ancient times, the method of teaching it does not have a long history. Although in the works of artists who lived in the past, such as Al-Khwarizmi, Farabi, Ibn Sina, Beruni, Zamakhshari, Navai, there are ideas related to education and training, it is not clear how to learn the native language. no thoughts related to learning. Al-Khwarizmi "Knowledge by feeling is partial knowledge, logical knowledge is truth", Abu Nasr Farabi "Knowledge, enlightenment, good morals make a knowledgeable, enlightened, mature, perfect person. For this, education must be properly organized, managed and directed by the teacher for specific purposes" is the main criterion in the methodology of teaching the Uzbek language.

By the beginning of the 20th century, European ones were added to traditional teaching methods. Local intellectuals such as Fitrat, Munavvar Kori, Khamza, A. Avloni, Kori Niyazov, Kayum Ramazan, Murad Shams, Majid Qadiri. In the 1940s, S.A. Fvessalonisky "Methods of teaching the native language". In the manual, a wide place is given to the development of speech and composition, and special attention is not paid to the methodology of teaching morphology and syntax. Since the 1940s, Uzbek scientists began to conduct research related to the problems of teaching languages. In 1944, M. Shams completed the study "Methods of teaching spelling", K. Khairullaev - "Typical spelling errors and their elimination."

In 1950, M. Shams published a manual "Methods of teaching the Uzbek language." In 1952, under the editorship of F. Kamal, the first part of the "Methods of teaching the Uzbek language" was published. In 1960, "Methods of teaching syntax and punctuation" by Kh. Rustamov and "Methods of teaching the Uzbek language" by N. Abdurakhmanov were published, in 1963. By 1975, Yu. Gulomov, I. Rasulov, Kh. Rustamov, B. Mirzaakhmedov created more advanced textbook. This textbook is also called "Methods of Teaching the Uzbek Language". This tutorial is still in use today. During the 1960s and 1980s, the body of work on methodology increased. At present, scientific research is being carried out on the methodology of teaching the native language.

The methodology of teaching the Uzbek language is, first of all, closely connected with philosophy and general linguistics, the theoretical foundations of linguistics.

First of all, the science of language determines the scientific basis and content of the native language subject studied at school. The correct organization and effectiveness of mother tongue teaching depend on scientific and accurate linguistic conclusions about the language. The methodology of teaching the native language and its development cannot be imagined without the science of linguistics.

The method of teaching the native language works in connection with the sciences of pedagogy and psychology. Pedagogy is a science that defines the principles of education. Educational principles are also applied in mother tongue lessons. The didactic part of pedagogical science is the theoretical basis of the method of teaching the native language, it is based on all the didactic principles of the method of teaching the native language.

In conclusion, we can say that the teacher needs to study the psychological abilities of his students, take them into account when explaining the materials of

the native language. The teacher must be able to arouse interest in his subject, attract their attention and use ways to memorize this material.

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